
LEADERSHIP STYLES AND LEARNING PROCESS IN PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN URUAN LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between leadership styles and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study examined the influence of authoritarian and permissive leadership styles on the learning process. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of all teachers in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area, from which a sample of 180 teachers was selected using simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a researcher-developed questionnaire titled Leadership Styles and Learning Process Questionnaire (LSLPQ), structured on a four-point Likert scale. The instrument was validated by experts in educational management, and its reliability was established using Cronbach Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.82. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that authoritarian leadership style has a significant negative relationship with the learning process ($r = -0.701$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that excessive control, rigid rules, and lack of teacher participation hinder effective teaching and pupil engagement. The study also found that permissive leadership style has a significant negative relationship with the learning process ($r = -0.412$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that lack of supervision and excessive freedom negatively affect classroom management and instructional coordination. Based on these findings, the study concluded that leadership style plays a critical role in shaping the effectiveness of the learning process in primary schools. It was therefore recommended that head teachers should adopt a balanced

leadership approach that combines appropriate control with teacher participation, while educational authorities should organize regular leadership training programmes to enhance instructional leadership and improve learning outcomes in public primary schools.

Keywords: *Authoritarian, Leadership styles, Learning process, Permissive*

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, education has been widely acknowledged as a fundamental instrument for national development and individual advancement. It plays a critical role in shaping human capital, promoting social cohesion, and fostering economic growth. Education is not only concerned with the acquisition of knowledge but also with the development of skills, attitudes, and values necessary for effective participation in society. As a dynamic process, it equips learners with cognitive, affective, and psychomotor competencies required for lifelong learning and adaptation to societal changes (Eze and Okon, 2022). In Nigeria, the National Policy on Education emphasizes that education is central to national development, as it fosters individual growth and societal transformation (FRN, 2013). Primary education represents the foundation of the entire educational system and serves as the first level of formal education. It is at this stage that children acquire basic literacy, numeracy, and communication skills that are essential for further learning. Udoh and Essien (2021) noted that primary education lays the groundwork for intellectual development and social integration, making it a critical stage in the educational process. The effectiveness of primary education depends largely on the quality of teaching and the administrative leadership provided by head teachers, who coordinate instructional activities and ensure the attainment of educational objectives.

Leadership in primary schools is a crucial factor that influences the teaching-learning process. It involves guiding, directing, and influencing teachers and pupils toward the achievement of educational goals. According to Northouse (2021), leadership is the process whereby an individual influences a group to achieve a common goal. In

the context of primary schools, the head teacher plays a central role in creating a conducive learning environment, supervising instructional activities, and motivating teachers to perform effectively. The leadership style adopted by the head teacher significantly affects teachers' instructional practices and pupils' learning outcomes. Leadership style refers to the pattern of behavior exhibited by a leader in directing and influencing subordinates. It determines how decisions are made, how communication flows, and how authority is exercised within the school. Among the various leadership styles, authoritarian and permissive leadership styles are commonly observed in primary schools. Authoritarian leadership style is characterized by strict control, centralized decision-making, and limited participation of subordinates. Olatunji and Akinyemi (2020) observed that authoritarian leaders enforce rules rigidly and expect compliance without seeking input from teachers. While this style may ensure discipline and order, it often limits creativity, reduces teacher motivation, and negatively affects the learning process. Permissive leadership style, on the other hand, is characterized by minimal control and a high level of freedom for subordinates. Leaders adopting this style allow teachers considerable autonomy in decision-making with little supervision. Ibrahim and Bello (2022) noted that permissive leadership can encourage creativity and independence; however, excessive freedom without proper guidance may lead to poor coordination, indiscipline, and ineffective instructional delivery. The learning process, which involves active interaction between teachers and pupils, is therefore significantly influenced by the leadership style adopted by the head teacher. This underscores the need to examine how authoritarian and permissive leadership styles affect the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The head teacher, as the leader of the primary school, is expected to provide effective leadership that promotes quality teaching and learning. This includes ensuring proper supervision of instructional activities, maintaining discipline, and creating a supportive learning environment. However, observations in public primary schools in

Uruan Local Government Area indicate that these expectations are not fully met. Some head teachers adopt authoritarian leadership styles characterized by rigid control, lack of teacher participation in decision-making, and excessive emphasis on rules. This often leads to low teacher morale, reduced creativity, and limited pupil engagement in classroom activities. As a result, the learning process becomes less effective, and pupils may not achieve the desired learning outcomes. Some head teachers adopt permissive leadership styles, allowing too much freedom without adequate supervision. This results in poor classroom management, indiscipline among pupils, and lack of coordination in instructional activities. Teachers may become less accountable, and the overall quality of teaching and learning may decline. These leadership challenges raise concerns about the effectiveness of the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area. Despite the importance of leadership in education, there is limited empirical evidence on how authoritarian and permissive leadership styles specifically influence the learning process in the area. This gap in knowledge necessitates the present study.

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate leadership styles and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area.

Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i) Determine the relationship between authoritarian leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area.
- ii) Determine the relationship between permissive leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area.

Research Questions

- I. What is the relationship between authoritarian leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area?

2. What is the relationship between permissive leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between authoritarian leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area.
2. There is no significant relationship between permissive leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area.

Design of the Study

Correlational research design was adopted for the study. According to Nworgu (2021), correlational research design is appropriate for determining the relationship between two or more variables. This design is suitable because the study seeks to establish the relationship between leadership styles and the learning process in public primary schools.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consists of all teachers in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 180 teachers was selected using simple random sampling technique. Schools were randomly selected, and teachers were chosen using balloting through a dice method to ensure equal chances of selection.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was a researcher-developed questionnaire titled Leadership Styles and Learning Process Questionnaire (LSLPQ). The instrument was structured on a four-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD), scored as 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The

instrument was validated by experts, and reliability was established using Cronbach Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.82.

Methods of Data Analysis

Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance using SPSS.

Results

Research Question One

What is the relationship between authoritarian leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area?

Table 1: Simple Correlation between authoritarian leadership style and learning process

Variables	N	r	Remark
Authoritarian Leadership Style	180	-0.701*	High negative relationship
Learning Process			

The result in Table 1 reveals an r-value of -0.701* which indicates a high negative relationship between authoritarian leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area. This implies that as authoritarian leadership practices increase, the effectiveness of the learning process decreases significantly. The finding suggests that rigid control, lack of teacher participation, and centralized decision-making negatively influence classroom interaction, teaching effectiveness, and pupil engagement.

Research Question Two

What is the relationship between permissive leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area?

Table 2: Simple Correlation between permissive leadership style and learning process

Variables	n	r	Remark
Permissive Leadership Style	180	-0.412*	Moderate negative relationship
Learning Process			

The result in Table 2 shows an r-value of -0.412* which indicates a moderate negative relationship between permissive leadership style and the learning process. This implies that excessive freedom, lack of supervision, and weak administrative control under permissive leadership negatively affect instructional coordination and classroom discipline, thereby reducing the effectiveness of the learning process.

Research Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between authoritarian leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of authoritarian leadership style and learning process

Variables	N	r-value	p-value	df	Decision at 0.05 level
Authoritarian Leadership Style	180	-0.701*	.000	178	Reject H ₀
Learning Process					

The analysis in Table 3 reveals that the p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance at 178 degrees of freedom. Based on this result, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is a statistically significant negative relationship between authoritarian leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area. This means that authoritarian leadership significantly undermines effective teaching and learning.

Research Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between permissive leadership style and the learning process in public primary schools in Uruan Local Government Area.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of permissive leadership style and learning process

Variables	N	r-value	p-value	df	Decision at 0.05 level
Permissive Leadership Style	180	-0.412*	0.000	178	Reject H ₀
Learning Process					

The analysis in Table 4 shows that the p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance at 178 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a statistically significant negative relationship between permissive leadership style and the learning process. This finding indicates that although permissive leadership allows freedom, excessive lack of control significantly reduces instructional effectiveness and classroom discipline.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings revealed that an authoritarian leadership style is significantly and negatively associated with the learning process. This relationship suggests that excessive control, rigid decision-making, and limited teacher participation tend to suppress instructional effectiveness and reduce learner engagement. In such environments, teachers often operate under strict directives with minimal autonomy, which can constrain creativity, limit instructional innovation, and ultimately weaken classroom interaction. This finding is consistent with the position of Olatunji and Akinyemi (2020), who reported that authoritarian leadership undermines collaborative instructional practices and reduces overall teaching effectiveness. The findings further indicated that a permissive leadership style also exerts a negative influence on the learning process when excessively applied. Although permissive leadership allows greater teacher freedom, insufficient supervision and weak administrative control can result in

poor classroom management, inconsistent instructional practices, and reduced academic discipline. Consequently, learning outcomes may decline due to lack of structure and inadequate monitoring of teaching activities. This observation supports the findings of Ibrahim and Bello (2022), who noted that overly relaxed leadership environments tend to weaken instructional accountability and reduce the effectiveness of the learning process.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that leadership style significantly influences the learning process in public primary schools. This implies that the manner in which head teachers lead and manage school activities plays a vital role in shaping the effectiveness of teaching and learning within the school environment. Leadership styles adopted by head teachers determine the level of teacher motivation, classroom supervision, instructional coordination, discipline, communication, and overall school climate, all of which directly or indirectly affect pupils' learning experiences and academic development. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

- I) Head teachers should adopt a balanced leadership approach.
- II) Government should organize leadership training programmes.
- III) Proper supervision should be maintained in schools.

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